

1 Mini Review

2 **Combustion Synthesis of Magnetic Nanomaterials for Biomed-**
3 **ical Applications**4 Harutyun Gyulasaryan¹, Astghik Kuzanyan¹, Aram Manukyan¹ and Alexander S. Mukasyan^{2,*}5 ¹ Institute for Physical Research of National Academy of Sciences of Armenia, Ashtarak-2, Ashtarak 0204,
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9 USA10 * Correspondence: amoukasi@nd.edu11 **Abstract:** Combustion synthesis (CS) is a green, energy-saving approach that allows easy scale-up
12 and continuous technologies. This process allows for synthesizing various nanoscale materials, in-
13 cluding oxides, nitrides, sulfides, metals, and alloys. In this work, we critically review the reported
14 results on CS of magnetic nanoparticles, focusing on their properties related to different bio appli-
15 cations. We also analyze challenges and suggest specific directions of research, which will allow
16 improving the properties and stability of materials fabricated by self-sustained reactions.17 **Keywords:** combustion synthesis, nanoparticles, magnetic properties, biomedical applications
1819 **1. Introduction**20 Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs) have attracted significant attention in recent years,
21 primarily in the field of biomedical applications [1-6]. These nanoparticles are highly effi-
22 cient in terms of their high surface area to volume ratio, chemical stability and easy surface
23 functionalization. The biocompatibility, rapid magnetic targeting, and high loading ca-
24 pacity of MNPs make them versatile in delivering therapeutic agents, improved multi-
25 modal imaging and in magnetic hyperthermia [7-19]. In combination with other NPs, they
26 also permit other bio applications, e.g. serving as antimicrobial agents.27 Specifically, the MNPs have demonstrated their potential to target drug delivery to
28 specific locations with precise tracking of drug distribution, bio-distribution, and metabo-
lism. Such materials offer a promising strategy for site-specific drug delivery for cancer-
ous tissues, inflammation, and cardiovascular diseases. The particles show excellent po-
tential in controlling the treatment of the disease while minimizing toxicity to healthy
cells. Magnetic nanoparticles also offer efficient separation of biomolecules and cells. The
magnetic properties of these nanoparticles allow them to immobilize biomolecules or cells
onto a magnetic surface [20-25]. Also, the MNPs can be used for imaging by exploiting
their magnetic properties. They offer improved image contrast and resolution due to their
magnetization behavior [26,27]. The goal of hyperthermia for cancer treatment is to in-
crease the temperature of the target tissue from 42° to 44°. This effect can be reached by
using magnetic nanoparticles, so-called magnetic hyperthermia [28,29]. The main chal-
lenges of this cancer therapy are the improvement of heating power of such nanoparticles
and the control of the local tumoral temperature.It was shown that synthesis method influences the properties of MNPs [30,31]. The
synthesis of MNPs involves various methods to achieve desired size, morphology, and
magnetic properties. The chemical precipitation method involves the precipitation of
metal ions from a salt solution by adding a reducing agent and a surfactant to control the
particle size and morphology. This method produces MNPs with small size and narrow29 **Citation:** To be added by editorial
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size distribution, but it requires high-temperature conditions and toxic reagents [32-35]. In the co-precipitation method, metal ions are co-precipitated from a salt solution by adding a reducing agent and a surfactant. The size and magnetic properties of the MNPs can be controlled by changing the pH and reaction time. This method is cost-effective and produces nanoparticles with good magnetic properties [36-38]. The sol-gel method involves the hydrolysis and condensation of metal alkoxides in a sol-gel matrix [39-44]. The size and morphology of the MNPs can be controlled by varying the precursor concentration, solvent, and reaction time. This method produces large quantities of nanoparticles with good magnetic properties, but it is time-consuming and requires high-temperature conditions. The microemulsion involves the use of a system, which consists of two immiscible phases (oil and water) and a surfactant [45-49]. Metal ions are reduced in the nanoscale droplets, resulting in MNPs with narrow size distribution and good magnetic properties. The process is relatively simple, fast, and produces MNPs with narrow particle size distribution. The hydrothermal method involves reacting metal salts in an autoclave under high temperature and pressure to create MNPs [50-53]. By modifying the reaction time, temperature, and precursor concentration, the size and shape of the nanoparticles can be controlled. Since this technique involves high-temperature conditions, it yields MNPs with excellent crystallinity.

Solution combustion synthesis (SCS) is a green, energy-saving approach that allows easy scale-up and continuous technologies [54]. SCS involves the self-sustained exothermic reactions along an aqueous or sol-gel media. This process allows for synthesizing various nanoscale materials, including oxides, nitrides, sulfides, metals, and alloys. In this work, we critically review the reported results on SCS of magnetic nanoparticles, focusing on their properties related to different bio applications. We also analyze challenges and suggest specific directions of research, which will allow improving the properties and stability of MNPs fabricated by the SCS method.

2. Solution Combustion Synthesis: Fundamentals

The solution combustion synthesis (SCS) method is based on the fundamental phenomenon, i.e., non-catalytic self-sustained exothermic reactions occurring in the solutions or gels [55]. Such reactive solutions generally involve oxidizer(s) and fuel(s) dissolved in a solvent. The typical types of used precursors are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Components of Reactive Solutions.

Oxidizer	Fuel	Solvent	Atmosphere
Metal nitrate hydrates $\text{Me}^{\text{v}}(\text{NO}_3)_{\text{v}} \cdot \text{nH}_2\text{O}$; (Me=Fe, Co, Ni, Mn, etc.) ⊙ - metal valency	Glycine ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$)	Water (H_2O)	Air
	Citric Acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$)	Benzene (C_6H_6)	Nitrogen
	Urea ($\text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$)	Ethanol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}$)	Oxygen
	Sucrose ($\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}$)	Methanol (CH_4O)	Inert gas:
	Glycose D-(+)- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$	Furfuryl alcohol: ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_6\text{O}_2$)	Argon
Metal Oxalates hydrates: $\text{Me}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot \text{nH}_2\text{O}$	Hydrazine ($\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{NH}_2$)	Formaldehyde: (CH_2O)	Helios
	Carbohydrazide ($\text{CH}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}$)	2-methoxyethanol ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$)	Vacuum
	Oxalyhydrazide ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$)		
Ammonium Nitrate: $\text{NH}_4(\text{NO}_3)$	Metal hydrazinecarboxylates hydrates: ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_5\text{Me}(\text{N}_2\text{H}_3\text{COO})_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where Me =		
	Fe, Co, Ni, Zn)		
Nitric acid (HNO_3)	Hexamethylenetetramine: ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$, HMTA)		
	Acetylacetone ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{O}_2$)		

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For example, in the Iron nitrate hydrates – HMTA system *in an argon atmosphere*, the following overall reaction occurs: $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 + n\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4$, which may lead to the formation of various magnetic phases [56]. The reaction is highly exothermic, and adiabatic combustion temperature (when neglecting the heat losses, T_{ad}) exceeds 2500 K. However, T_{ad} can be controlled by varying amounts of water (n) and fuel to oxidizer *molar ratio* ϕ $\phi = \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4/\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$. Indeed, at $\phi=1$, i.e., stoichiometric ratio and $n=0$, $T_{\text{ad}}=2630$ K, while at $n = 4$ and $\phi=4$, it is below 1000 K (Figure 1a). Correspondingly, the phase composition of the solid-state product changes (Figure 1b). The wide specter of magnetic phases, including Fe, Fe_3O_4 , Fe_3C , and Fe_3N , can be synthesized in the same system by optimizing combustion parameters (n, ϕ). Close to stoichiometry ($\phi=1$), the Fe_3O_4 phase is in equilibrium, while at large ϕ , the Fe_3C prevails. The narrow parametric n - ϕ region corresponds to the formation of the pure iron phase.

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Figure 1. Calculated adiabatic temperature (a) and equilibrium solid products (b) for $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 - \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ system vs fuel/oxidizer molar ratio (ϕ) and amount of water (n) (adopted from [56]). The above features delineate a versatility of the SCS approach.

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Figure 2. Different SCS mode: (a) Volume Combustion Synthesis; (b) Self-propagating high temperature synthesis; (c) impregnated SCS; (d) cellulose-assisted SCS; (e) templated SCS; (f) spray SCS (g) SCS of thin films (adopted from [57])

The other important feature is that SCS can be accomplished in different reaction modes [55, 57]. The most widely used mode is the so-called volume SCS (Figure 2a). In this case, a solution poured into the chemical vessel is uniformly preheated to the self-ignition, which takes place essentially along the whole reactive volume. Example of a time-temperature profile for VSCS in $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ – glycine system ($\phi=1$) is shown in Figure 3a [58]. It can be seen that in this mode, the duration of the high-temperature stage IV is extremely short. In the case of the self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS) mode (Figure 2b), a solution (or reactive gel formed after drying) is locally ($\sim 1\text{mm}^3$) pre-heated and high-temperature reaction front propagates along the media. The width of the high-temperature SHS zone is more comprehensive as compared to that of the VSCS (Figure 3b) [59].

Figure 3. Typical temperature time profiles for different SCS modes: (a) VSCS; (b) SHS; (c) impregnated SCS – inert substrate; (d) cellulose assisted SCS (adopted from [58]; [59]; [60]; [62]).

The liquid state of the reaction media permits different types of impregnated SCS modes (Figure 2 c-d). The solution can be impregnated into the inert porous media, followed by reaction initiation (Figure 2c). In this case, the maximum reaction temperature is lower as compared to SHS mode because of the inert dilution of the system (Figure 3c; [60]). This approach was used to prepare high-specific surface area catalysts [61]. The solution can be impregnated into active porous media, i.e., cellulose [62,63]. Cellulose-impregnated SCS can be used for low exothermic systems because the combustion of cellulose contributes to total heat release. In dependence on the burning rates of the cellulose and the reactive solution, the former may precede or follow the latter (Figure 3d; [62, 64]). Last version of the impregnated mode is templated-SCS (Figure 2e). In this case, a solution is impregnated into the media with desired pore size distribution, e.g., silica nanotubes. After a self-sustained reaction, the template is removed by dissolution in an appropriate solvent, while synthesized particles have narrow size distribution corresponding to the nanotubes' diameter [65].

The other unusual mode is so-called spray solution combustion, which combines concepts of SCS and aerosol spray pyrolysis (Figure 2f). In this case, the aqueous reaction solution was placed in the chamber of the inhaler and sprayed into a tubular furnace by a carrier gas (argon, nitrogen, air). The initial liquid spheres are combusted and converted to the ideal solid, hollow spheres with diameters controlled by the diameter of the initial droplet and wall thickness in the range of 10–20 nm [58]. Finally, the reactive solution can be used for the fabrication of thin coatings (Figure 2g). The reactive solution is spin-coated onto the desired substrate, followed by reaction initiation in the layer [66,67].

Above modes were for fabrication of variety of high surface area materials and nano particles, including oxides, metals, alloys, nitrides and carbides [54, 55]. Below, we overview reports, which were dedicated to the SCS of the nanoparticles focusing on their magnetic properties.

3. Solution Combustion Synthesis of Magnetic Compounds

3.1. Iron oxide based materials

The iron oxide magnetic particles were fabricated by SCS using citric acid as a fuel. The aqueous solution of ferric nitrate nonahydrate, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and citric acid, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$, mixed in a molar ratio of 6:5 ($\varphi = 0.8$) was used as a reactive media [58]. The reaction can be represented as follows:

Two heating sources were used: (i) a heating mantle with a temperature of 450 °C; (ii) a microwave oven (245GHz, 800W). In both cases, the volume SCS mode was accomplished. Unfortunately, the actual synthesis conditions, i.e., the process's temperature time history, were not reported. We understand the complications associated with temperature measurements during SCS, but it is a critical issue for controlling the microstructure and, thus, properties of the obtained materials.

Based on the X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, it was concluded that the heating procedure significantly influences the phase composition of the produced powders. In the case of heating in the mantle, the product (P1) involved primarily (97%) magnetite (Fe_3O_4). While in the case of the microwave heating it (P2) was primarily (85%) maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$) (Table 2). It is worth noting that it is difficult to resolve these two phases by XRD analysis; typically, FTIR analysis is used to support the conclusion. It is vital when the crystallinity of the powder is not high, as it was observed for powder produced by micro oven heating (see also Figure 3 in [68]).

Table 2. Some characteristics of the iron oxide nanoparticles (adopted from [68]).

Sample	Heating	Phase composition wt.%	Crystallite size, nm	S_{BET} m ² /g	Average pore diameter, nm
P1	Mantle	97% Fe_3O_4 +3% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$	23	42	7.1
P2	Microwave	85% $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ +11% Fe_3O_4 +2% FeO +2%Fe	5	71	5.5

The TEM images of both products are shown in Figure 4. The medium particle size was 15 and 11 nm for P1 and P2, respectively. Correspondingly, the BET-specific surface area was 42 and 71 m²/g. Logically, both powders possess superparamagnetic behavior with saturation magnetization 67(P1) and 42(P2) emu/g.

164 **Figure 4.** TEM images of powders synthesized by VSCS: (a) Mantle heating; (b) Microwave (adopted from [68])
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166 For biomedical applications (diagnostic and therapy), the magnetic nanoparticles
167 must exhibit superparamagnetic behavior at room temperature, biocompatible surface
168 coatings, and colloidal stability in an aqueous carrier [30]. Based on the structural charac-
169 teristics, P2 particles were selected for the preparation of colloidal solutions by using dif-
170 ferent surfactants and solvents. Figure 5 represents the results recorded for four colloidal
171 suspensions in terms of their particle size distribution. It can be seen that all the colloidal
172 suspensions possess a unimodal particle size distribution with an average hydrodynamic
173 diameter of 90 nm (O/W – line 1); 105 nm (O/PBS – line 2 and T/W – line 3), and 80 nm
174 (T/PBS – line 4).

175 **Figure 5.** The intensity distribution of particles size (DLS) of different colloidal suspensions (O –
176 Oleic acid; W – distilled water; T – Tween 80; PBS phosphate buffered saline) (adopted from [68])
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178 The characteristics of the colloidal solution are presented in Table 3. Pure Oleic acid
179 provides a higher absolute value for negative Zeta potential, indicating higher stability of
180 the colloidal suspension. In addition, the lower polydispersity index (PDI) suggests better
181 homogeneity of the media. *The work demonstrates that SCS is a versatile method for the syn-
182 thesis of iron oxide nanoparticles on the order of 10 nm, which allows the fabrication of stable col-
183 loidal suspensions.*

184 **Table 3.** Some characteristics of colloidal suspensions.

Sample	Surfactant	Dispersion Media	Diameter, nm	PDI	Zeta potential mV
O/W	Oleic acid	Water	91	0.179	-74
O/PBS	Oleic acid	PBS	105	0.326	-47
O/W	Oleic acid + Tween80	Water	105	0.315	-14
O/W	Oleic acid + Tween 80	PBS	79	0.189	-12

The aqueous solution of ferric nitrate nonahydrate, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and citric acid, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7$ but with molar ratio $\phi=3$, was used to fabricate $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ particles [69]. The particles were produced in volume SCS mode, putting the solution on the hot plate preheated to 500°C . Again, the time temperature of the process was not reported. A well-crystalline rhombohedral $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ phase with a crystallinity size of $\sim 27\text{ nm}$ was obtained. The particles possess spherical morphology with an average diameter of $\sim 75\text{ nm}$. These particles were also mixed with thin 2D-carbon-flakes having a size of $\sim 2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$.

The cellular toxicity of $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$, carbon nano-plates, and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}$ nanocomposites was studied using MTT assay and nuclear imaging based on the cell morphological changes on both human lung cancer cell line A549 and a non-cancerous cell line. The relative cell viability (%) was estimated. The results demonstrated that the pure and composite material exhibited above 70% viability on non-cancerous cell lines and around 60% inhibition on A549 lung cancer, indicating the $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3/\text{C}$ nanocomposite is biocompatible and can be used for biological applications and anticancer therapy.

The reagents used for the SCS of Fe_3O_4 (magnetite) and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (maghemite) nanoparticles and their colloidal suspensions were: $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as an oxidizing agent, citric acid, and glucose D-(+)- $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6$, as fuels and oleic acid ($\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$), as surfactant [70]. The synthesis procedure was not described in detail. Using citric acid as a fuel led to the formation of the magnetite phase, while glucose resulted in the synthesis of $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ particles. It is worth noting that the latter contradicts the work results from which the synthesis protocol was utilized, where both fuels led to the formation of Fe_3O_4 . The TEM images of the Fe_3O_4 and $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ particles are shown in Figure 6. The characteristics of the powders are presented in Table 4.

Figure 6. TEM images of (a) Fe_3O_4 and (b) $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ particles (adopted from [70])

Table 4. Characteristics of iron oxide powders [70].

Sample	Crystallite size, nm	S_{BET} m^2/g	Average diameter Nm	Saturation magnetization emu/g	Remnant magnetization emu/g	Coercively kA/m
Fe_3O_4	18	56	21	57.7	4.5	5.2
$\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$	5	149	8	41.5	0.7	1.0

The authors were able to create a stable colloidal suspension from the particles by using oleic acid as a surfactant and water and PBS as solvent media. It was more important to test their effects in vitro on human keratinocytes (HaCat cells) and in vivo by employing an animal model of acute dermal toxicity. They found a lack of toxicity for normal human cells induced by the iron oxide nanoparticles colloidal suspensions after an exposure of

216 24 h. The dermal acute toxicity test showed that the applications of the colloidal suspen-
 217 sions on female and male SKH-1 hairless mice were not associated with significant
 218 changes in the quality of skin function. *The above works prove that 10-70 nm spherical biocom-*
 219 *patible nanoparticles of different iron oxides can be fabricated by SCS.*

220 Can one synthesize by using SCS the iron oxide particles below 10 nm and narrow
 221 particle size distribution? The use of the template SCS approach provides a positive an-
 222 swer to the question [65]. The mesoporous silica (SBA-15) was used as a template (Figure
 223 7 a,b). The iron nonahydrate – glycine – ammonium nitrate aqueous solution was impreg-
 224 nated into the porous high surface area BET~780 m²/g) template, which involves channels
 225 with a diameter ~ 6nm ±0.2 nm.

226
 227 **Figure 7.** TEM images of (a,b) SBA template and (c,d) Fe₂O₃ nano particles synthesized in SHS mode
 228 (adopted from [65])

229 A TEM image (Figure 7c) of combustion products after leaching the template indi-
 230 cates that ~95% of hematite particles are smaller than 5 nm, with an average size of ~3.5
 231 nm. High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) image (Figure 7d) provides information on the
 232 atomic structure and morphology of α-Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles. The interplanar spacing of
 233 0.27 nm corresponds to the d₁₀₄ spacing between (104) atomic planes of the crystal struc-
 234 ture. It was shown that because of the ultralow sizes and high crystallinity, the combustion-
 235 derived α-Fe₂O₃ nanoparticles exhibit superparamagnetic properties in the tempera-
 236 ture range of 70–300 K. The high specific surface area (132 m²/g) of the powder indicates
 237 the vital role of surface magnetic spins resulting in high magnetization at 300 K.

238 The results above demonstrate that iron oxide nanoparticles in the range size from 4
239 to 100 nm and any desired phase compositions can be successfully fabricated by SCS. Ob-
240 tained particles were shown to be biocompatible and allow the preparation of stable col-
241 loidal suspension. The following research stage should involve extensive in vivo and in
242 vitro studies of such MNPs for different biomedical applications.
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244 3.2. Nickel oxide and Ni-based Alloys

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246 Solution combustion synthesis of nickel oxide (NiO) is a “classical” process, which
247 was widely used to investigate the intrinsic mechanism of self-sustained chemical reac-
248 tions in homogeneous solutions (cf. [71,72]). Different fuels, shown in Table 1, were used
249 to fabricate NiO nanoparticles. The nickel nitrite – glycine system was the first one leading
250 to the formation of pure Ni in the combustion wave [71]. However, a recent publication
251 suggested the exotic fuel, i.e., Areca catechu leaf extract [73]. The Areca catechu leaf ele-
252 mental composition is as follows: Carbon (55 wt%); Oxygen 36 wt%; Potassium 4 wt%,
253 chlorine (2.5 wt%) silicon (1 wt%) and calcium (0.7 wt%). The SCS was accomplished in
254 VSCS mode with a furnace temperature of 500° C. Well crystalline FCC NiO phase pos-
255 sesses a crystalline size of ~5.6 nm. The SEM and TEM images of the particles are shown
256 in Figure 8, indicating that powder agglomerates that involve particles with a size of ~ 10
257 nm.

258 **Figure 8.** SEM (a) and TEM (b) images of NiO particles (adopted from [73]).

259 In the human digestive system, pancreatic α -amylase is a critical enzyme that cata-
260 lyzes the initial step in the hydrolysis of starch. It is the primary source of glucose in the
261 diet. The α -amylase inhibitor effectiveness of synthesized NiO NPs was compared with
262 the standard drug Metformin. The Metformin showed inhibitory effects on α -amylase
263 activity with a concentration of test drug needed to inhibit cell growth by 50% (IC_{50}) of 232
264 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The IC_{50} value of the extract was found to be 268 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. As-synthesized NiO NPs
265 showed significant anticancer activity with 93 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ at 50% inhibition concentration
266 against the human lung cancer cell line (A549). The biological assay results revealed that
267 NiO NPs exhibited significant cytotoxicity against human lung cancer cells, showing con-
268 siderable cell viability.

269 In a recent publication [74], authors report the SCS of CoCuNi alloy, which possesses
270 the morphology of hollow spheres (Figure 9). The spray SCS mode (Figure 2f) was used
271 to produce such a unique structure. The outer diameter of the spheres was in the range of
272 0.2-2 μm , and the thickness of the CoCuNi shell is the range of 10-30 nm. The crystallinity
273 size was around ~ 18 nm. It was worth noting that the same composition with crystallinity
274 size ~ 35 nm was obtained in SHS mode (Figure 2b).
275

Figure 9. SEM (a,b) and TEM (c) images with ED and EDX diagnostics (adopted from [74]).

The magnetic properties of the alloy, obtained under optimal synthesis conditions: ($\phi = 1.25$ for the SHS mode and $\phi = 3$, $T_{\text{furn}} = 1000$ °C and carrier gas flow rate 2 L/min) were studied at room temperature in a magnetic field range of ± 15000 Oe (see Figure 6 in [74]). The particles were shown to possess high saturation magnetization in the range of 65–75 emu/g. In combination with unique morphologies, such particles may be good candidates for drug delivery applications.

The above data suggest that Ni-based nano-structured materials can be synthesized by using different SCS modes. It is more important that the knowledge of the reaction mechanism in the system allows controlling the morphology of the obtained particles and thus controlling their physical and chemical properties desirable for different bio applications.

3.3. Complex oxides

Solution combustion synthesis is a powerful tool for fabricating complex oxides with attractive magnetic properties. For example, sub micrometric (250–330 nm) BiFeO_3 particles were produced using volume combustion synthesized mode [75]. The bismuth nitrate pentahydrate, $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, iron nitrate nonahydrate, $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, diluted nitric acid were used as the oxidizing agents, and glycine as a fuel. The balanced chemical reaction can be written as follows:

The n and p coefficients represent the number of glycine and nitric acid moles used per mole of $\text{Bi}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively. They specifically focused on varying ratios between NO_3^- ions and glycine from 10 to 3.6. It is worth noting that all synthesized powders were post-annealed first at 350 °C for 2 h and then at 500 °C for 2 h. Finally, the powders were

299 heat treated at 600 °C for 3 h. These annealing processes were performed in an ambient
300 (air) atmosphere.

301 The XRD analysis of all powders indicates the formation of a rhombohedral BiFeO₃
302 phase with a size of the crystallite range of 35 to 60 nm. Figure 10 shows the typical mi-
303 crostructures of the powders after annealing at 600°C. The materials involve well-faceted
304 crystals in the few nanometers to a few hundred of nanometers size range. It can be seen
305 that BiFeO₃ powders synthesized with the high oxidizing/reducing agent ratio (10, 7.4,
306 and 5.2; Figure 10 a, b, c) possess wider particle size distribution, as compared to that
307 fabricated at the ratio of 3.6 (Figure 10 d).
308

309 **Figure 10.** Typical SEM images of BiFeO₃ samples synthesized using four oxidizing/reducing agent
310 ratios: 10 (a), 7.4 (b), 5.2 (c), and 3.6 (d); the length of the scale bar is 100 nm (adopted from [75]).

311 Figure 11 shows the room temperature magnetization curves along with the zero-
312 field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetization of the different BiFeO₃ powders.
313 The ZFC and FC curves were recorded between 1.8 and 300 K under an applied magnetic
314 field of 500 Oe. The shape of the magnetization curves for the latter samples exhibit char-
315 acteristics of an antiferromagnetic material. In contrast, the magnetization curve of the
316 BiFeO₃-3.6 sample displays a combination of antiferromagnetic and superparamagnetic
317 features. The existence of ferromagnetic ordering in all powders was confirmed by esti-
318 mating the coercive field at different temperatures, as presented in Table 5. The coercivity
319 of all the samples increased with the decrease in temperature, as occurs in ferromagnetic
320 materials. Overall, the values of the coercive fields are low.

321 **Table 5.** Coercive Fields (Oe) of BiFeO₃ Samples at Different Temperatures

Sample	1.8 K	60 K	100 K	200 K	300K
BiFeO ₃ -10	734	330	195	108	80
BiFeO ₃ -7.4	1207	484	284	178	172
BiFeO ₃ -5.2	1226	692	529	353	288
BiFeO ₃ -3.6	1561	827	594	321	198

The BiFeO₃ particles synthesized at the oxidizing/reducing agent ratio of 3.6 have a room-temperature magnetic moment almost twice those synthesized at higher ratios (Figure 11a). The microstructure of the particles explained this effect. Specifically, the BiFeO₃-3.6 sample consists of well-crystalline submicron particles of ~100 nm size, which favors the increase in magnetization by uncompensated spins at the surface or grain boundaries.

Figure 11. (a) Magnetization versus applied magnetic field curves at 300 K and (b) zero-field-cooled (ZFC) and field-cooled (FC) magnetization curves (under 500 Oe applied magnetic field) for the BiFeO₃ samples (adopted from [75]).

Thus, it was concluded that by adjusting the oxidizing/reducing agent ratio to 3.6, which corresponds to an oxidizing/reducing agent equivalence ratio (ϕ) close to 0.5, it was possible to avoid the formation of typical impurity phases such as Bi₂Fe₄O₉ in the samples and significantly improve magnetic properties. Moreover, the phase-pure BiFeO₃ particles manifest higher splitting temperatures between their ZFC and FC magnetization curves and moderate coercive field, which lead to their stable antiferromagnetic behavior over a wide temperature range (2–300K; Figure 11b).

Another example is the solution combustion synthesis of nano-scale ferrites. Specifically, CoFe₂O₄; NiFe₂O₄; Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ ferrite NPs were fabricated by SCS using cobalt, nickel and iron nitrates precursors as the oxidizing agent and glycine as a fuel [76]. The powder samples obtained in the solution combustion process were annealed in an air atmosphere at 600 °C for 2 h.

The typical microstructures of the synthesized powders are shown in Figure 12. It can be seen that the nanoparticles formed in NiFe₂O₄ sample are smaller than that for CoFe₂O₄ powder, and the particles formed in Ni_{0.5}Co_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ are of intermediate sizes. It was estimated that the average size of the particles in the CoFe₂O₄, NiFe₂O₄, and Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ samples are 40 ± 10 nm, 26 ± 8 nm, and 32 ± 7 nm, respectively.

Figure 12. SEM images of the (a) CoFe₂O₄, (b) NiFe₂O₄, (c) Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ nanoparticles (adopted from [76]).

The XRD patterns of the samples synthesized with a nitrate ions/glycine ratio of 3 revealed the formation of CoFe₂O₄, NiFe₂O₄, and Co_{0.5}Ni_{0.5}Fe₂O₄ ferrites. Magnetization

curves of the CoFe_2O_4 , NiFe_2O_4 , and $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles were investigated at different temperatures. The hysteresis loops of CoFe_2O_4 NPs show typical characteristics of hard ferrimagnetic material, whereas the magnetization curves of NiFe_2O_4 NPs correspond to soft ferromagnetic material (Figure 13a). The room-temperature saturation magnetizations (M_s) of the CoFe_2O_4 , NiFe_2O_4 and $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ were 53, 30, 44 emu/g, respectively. The magnetic coercivity (H_c) of NiFe_2O_4

NPs was only 159 Oe at room temperature, but it significantly increases to 886 Oe when half of the Ni^{2+} cations are replaced by Co^{2+} cations, resulting in $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ nanoparticles. The effects of phase purity and stoichiometry on the catalytic behavior of the metal ferrites were studied by evaluating their reduction efficiency of 4-nitrophenol, a common organic contaminant in wastewater. The phase-impure NiFe_2O_4 sample, which featured segregated metallic Ni clusters on its surface, exhibited exceptional performance in the reduction of 4-nitrophenol.

Figure 13. (a), Magnetization vs applied magnetic field curves at 300 K for CoFe_2O_4 -6, NiFe_2O_4 -6, and $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ -6; (b) UV-vis absorption spectra correspond to the progressive reduction of 4-nitrophenol to 4-aminophenol using the NiFe_2O_4 -3 sample as catalyst (b) (adopted from [76]).

As a final example, let us overview the SCS of other $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Me}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (Me = Mn and Zn) ferrites [77]. These ferrites along with CoFe_2O_4 were synthesized by using $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Mn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, and $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ as oxidizers and oxalyl dihydrazide (ODH: $\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$) as a fuel. Volume reaction mode was used with a furnace temperature of 400°C . It is worth noting that no additional calcination stages were applied.

The diffraction patterns revealed no impurities associated with the corresponding metal oxides. The estimated values of the crystallite size and lattice microstrain of the synthesized ferrites are presented in Table 6. The average crystallite sizes of ferrites are in the range between 16 to 28 nm, suggesting the nanocrystalline nature of the synthesized materials. The work illustrated that well-crystalline complex oxides could be obtained directly by SCS without additional heat treatments.

Table 6. Crystallite sizes, lattice parameters, X-ray densities of ferrites (adopted from [77])

Sample	Crystallite size nm	Micro strain	Lattice Parameters Å	X-ray Density g/cm^3
CoFe_2O_4	17	0.00245	8.403	5.21
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	28	0.00178	8.428	5.13
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	26	0.00154	8.371	5.25
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	16	0.00055	8.444	5.21

The particle size distributions of the powders obtained by analysis of low-magnification TEM images are shown in Figure 14. A log-normal distribution function fitted the

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obtained histograms, and the maximum peak value has been considered the average nanoparticle size, which ranges from 25 nm to 30 nm. High-resolution microscopic images have also been obtained (Figure 15). Analysis of HERT images, as well as FFT patterns, confirmed the formation of cubic crystallinity for each composition

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Figure 14. The particle size distribution histograms of the ferrites: (a) CoFe_2O_4 , (b) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, (c) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, and (d) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (adopted from [77]).

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Magnetic hysteresis loops of different ferrites at room temperature are shown in Figure 16. The obtained behavior confirms the ferromagnetic nature of the ferrites. Various data, such as saturation magnetization (M_s), remanent magnetization (M_r), coercivity (H_c), and remanence ratio or squareness ratio (M_r/M_s) values, were obtained from the hysteresis loops and are presented in Table 7. Among the considered ferrites, $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ exhibits the highest saturation magnetization value of 76 emu/g, while CoFe_2O_4 has the lowest value of ~50 emu/g.

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Figure 15. HRTEM images of (a) CoFe_2O_4 , (b) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, (c) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, and (d) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$. Fourier filtered images of the selected areas from the micrographs are given. The inset shows the FFT of the selected area (adopted from [77]).

Dielectric measurements were performed at room temperature in the frequency range of 100 Hz-50 MHz. The dielectric measurements indicate that the dielectric value decreases with increasing frequency, and the ac conductivity increases at higher frequencies due to the mobilization of charge carriers. CoFe_2O_4 shows the highest dielectric loss among all the investigated materials. In addition, the dielectric losses of the ferrites appeared to be reasonably low (0.1-2.35) in the measured frequency region. It is also observed that doping the parent CoFe_2O_4 nano-ferrite by Mn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , or Zn^{2+} , leads to the decrease of the dielectric constant values.

Figure 16. M-H curves: (a) CoFe_2O_4 , (b) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, (c) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, (d) $\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ (adopted from [77]).

Table 7. Magnetic properties of the ferrites obtained at $H = 5000$ Oe and room temperature (adopted from [77]).

Sample	M_s emu/g	M_r emu/g	M_r / M_s	H_c Oe
CoFe_2O_4	49.7	12.7	0.26	290
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Mn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	67.1	36.1	0.54	1463
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Ni}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	58.4	32.2	0.55	1988
$\text{Co}_{0.5}\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$	76.1	27.6	0.36	471

Thus, it was demonstrated that SCS is a versatile method for synthesizing complex oxides in a wide range of particle sizes and attractive magnetic properties, which can be optimized by doping ferrites. However, this method also allows the fabrication of various nanomaterials that, combined with magnetic phases, fit different bio-applications.

3.4. Zinc oxide

Zinc oxide (ZnO) may serve as an inorganic antimicrobial agent, which is recognized as safe under US FDA listings for humans. Based on the literature, we may conclude that SCS can produce ZnO particles of various morphology and size [78-85]. Typically, zinc nitrate hexahydrate ($\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) with different fuels was used for the synthesis. Let us consider several examples.

Zinc oxide nanomaterials doped with Ag, Au were synthesized by using urea as a fuel, silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , 98.9%), and tetra chloroauric-III-acid hydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 98%) for doping [81]. VSCS made was used with a furnace temperature of 500°C . The sub-micron (100-500 nm) flower-like 3D particles with Au and Ag uniformly distributed on the surface with an average cluster size of 3-10 nm were synthesized.

The antimicrobial study of the such NPs was performed on gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus*, while antifungal tests were carried out with the yeast *Eremothecium ashbyii*. The results of testing of particles' photocatalytic activities show that Ag-doped ZnO nanomaterial has a degradation efficiency of 45%

against methylene blue. Antimicrobial and antifungal activity studies have shown that pure ZnO is more effective against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, and Ag-doped ZnO is more effective against *Eremothecium ashbyii*.

Fuels available in nature, i.e., aqueous leaf extracts of *Abutilon indicum*, *Melia azedarach*, *Indigofera tinctoria*, as well as lactose monohydrate ($C_{12}H_{22}O_{11} \cdot H_2O$) were used to fabricate the ZnO nanoparticles by using Volume SCS method [82]. The fuel-to-oxidizer ratio is varied, but estimating the ϕ values from the reported data is difficult. The furnace temperature was 375 ± 10 °C. XRD analysis suggests that fabricated particles possess high crystallinity. TEM images of different ZnO particles are presented in Figure 17, and some parameters extracted from XRD and BET measurements are shown in Table 8. The average particle size of ZnO (Lactose), ZnO (*Abutilon indicum*), ZnO (*Melia azedarach*), and ZnO (*Indigofera tinctoria*) was found to be 26, 15, 12, and 21 nm, respectively.

Figure 17. TEM images of the ZnO particles obtained with different fuels (a) lactose; (b) *A. indicum*; (c) *M. azedarach*; (d) *I. tinctoria* (adopted from [82]).

Table 8. Magnetic properties of the ferrites obtained at $H = 5000$ Oe and room temperature (adopted from [77]).

Sample	Crystallite size, nm	S_{BET} m ² /g	BJH, average pore diameter, Å
ZnO(L)	13	19	91
ZnO(A)	11	26	83
ZnO(M)	9	90	56
ZnO(I)	11	38	72

Data from the MTT assay in DU-145 and Calu-6 cells indicate that all ZnO NPs induced dose-dependent toxicity in both cells. However, the materials prepared using aqueous leaf extracts as fuels exhibited better activity than those synthesized using lactose as fuel. Among all the NPs, ZnO (M) prepared using the aqueous extract of leaves of *M. azedarach* showed higher anticancer activity in both DU-145 and Calu-6 cells. This effect is probably related to the higher surface area of these particles (see Table 8). In addition, the results of cytotoxicity studies by hemolysis assay suggest that all ZnO NPs fabricated by SCS are biocompatible at their lower concentration, up to 2.5 mg/mL.

The above examples indicate that SCS is a powerful tool for the synthesis of ZnO nanoparticles in a wide range of sizes (12–500 nm). It also allows easy doping of such particles with any desired elements (see also [83–85]).

3.5. Calcium-based compounds

Calcium phosphates (CaPs)-based ceramics are promising candidates for biomedical and orthopedic applications [86]. However, the poor biodegradability of some CaPs, such as hydroxyapatite, keeps the task challenging. There are two approaches to enhancing the ceramic properties: (i) doping; (b) developing a novel synthesis method [87]. In this regard, doping and the SCS method is an attractive passway.

For example, the CaP nanostructure was fabricated by SCS, using calcium nitrate tetrahydrate $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck), and di-ammonium hydrogen phosphate $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ (Alfa Aesar) as oxidizers, glycine $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$ (Merck) as fuel and nitric acid HNO_3 as a catalyst [88]. The reactive aqueous solution was heated to a temperature of 60°C for total evaporation of the solvent. Subsequently, the temperature was increased to 140°C until the initiation of the combustion reaction. The obtained ash was calcined at 800°C for 2 h.

XRD analysis of the ash revealed the formation of two main phases: hydroxyapatite and some amount of beta-tricalcium phosphate (HA/ β TCP), with traces of calcium pyrophosphate. The later phase disappeared after calcination. The typical microstructures of the powder are shown in Figure 18.

Figure 18. SEM images the CaP powder obtained by SCS and heat-treated at 800°C for 2 hours. It can be seen that the aggregates of about $5\ \mu\text{m}$ in size involve nanoparticles of spherical morphology and average grain size $43 \pm 1\ \text{nm}$ (adopted from [88]).

Thus produced CaP powder was used as a potential encapsulate or photodynamic support for photoactive drugs, using hypericin (HY) as a photosensitizer agent. It was demonstrated that $54 \pm 1.2\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ is the amount of CaP particles loaded with HY in the presence of light needed for reducing the parasites population by half. This value is low compared to the amount of free HY (about $458\ \mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) needed to exhibit an EC_{50} effect.

The Si-doped CaP ceramics were fabricated by SCS using calcium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), ammonium dihydrogen phosphate $(\text{NH}_4)(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)$, and tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS) ($\text{Si}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4$) as precursors [89]. The glycine and citric acid were employed as fuels. For all compositions, the Ca/ (P + Si) (Si = 0, 0.1, 0.4 moles) ratio was adjusted to 1.67. The TEOS was hydrolyzed in the presence of HNO_3 and deionized water (TEOS : water : HNO_3 volume ratio was 1:4:1). The solutions were sequentially supplemented with calcium nitrate ($0.5\ \text{mg}/\text{ml}$), ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ($0.14\ \text{mg}/\text{ml}$), and fuel ($0.14\ \text{mg}/\text{ml}$), and heated up to about 330°C using a digital hot plate.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns showed the presence of primary hydroxyapatite and some amount of beta-tricalcium phosphate (HA/ β TCP) in all synthesized samples. Crystallographic parameters of crystalline phases are presented in Table 9. Crystallite sizes of HA and β TCP in the powders synthesized using glycine and citric acid were about 15 nm and 43 nm, respectively. It can be seen that doping does not influence the crystal structure while using glycine slightly increases the powder crystallinity.

Table 9. Semi-quantification results on crystallinity, phases, crystallite and particle size (adopted from [89]).

Fuel	Amount of Si, mole	Crystallinity %	HA wt.%	β TCP wt.%	Crystallite size HA, nm	Crystallite size β TCP, nm	Particle size, nm
Glycine	0	59	90	10	15.6	42.4	68 \pm 6
	0.4	52	86	14	15.6	42.4	60 \pm 4
Citric Acid	0	55	74	26	14.2	42.4	84 \pm 12
	0.4	50	94	6	14.2	42.4	54 \pm 8

The specific surface areas (SSA) for the undoped powders synthesized using glycine and citric acid are about 38 and 20 m²/g, respectively. Doping leads to an increase in the SSA. Indeed, powders synthesized using glycine with 0.1 and 0.4 moles of Si⁴⁺ possess the specific surface area 146 and 97 m²/g, respectively. When the fuel is citric acid, doping with 0.1 and 0.4 moles of Si⁴⁺ changes the specific surface area to 34 and 25 m²/g, respectively. The TRM images of the powders are presented in Figure 19. It can be seen that doped particles possess a much more porous structure, influencing the specific surface area.

Figure 19. TEM micrographs of the powders synthesized using glycine (un-doped (a), doped with 0.1 (b), and 0.4 (c) mole Si⁴⁺ ions), and citric acid (un-doped (d), doped with 0.1 (e), and 0.4 mol (f) Si⁴⁺ ions) (adopted from [89]).

Bioactivity, cell viability, bone-like nodule formation ability, biodegradability and cell attachment studies were accomplished by using Simulated Body Fluid (SBF) media. For example, to evaluate bioactivity, the so-called, dynamic surface tension (SFT) of the SBF medium containing the NPs were measured using Du Noüy ring method. Based on the SFT results, the relative number of bioactivity was estimated as follows:

$$\beta = \frac{\text{Final SFT} - \text{SFT of SBT}}{\text{SFT of SBF}} \cdot 100\% \quad (3)$$

It was shown that the bioactivity of the Si-doped sample with 0.1 mole Si⁴⁺ synthesized using glycine was 255%, i.e., 2.5 times higher than of undoped samples. However, the bioactivity of Si-doped samples synthesized using citric acid was less than 100%. The difference in the release of Ca ions explained the effect. The better ionic dissolution in the

case of the powders synthesized using glycine might stem from their larger specific surface area, more oxygen defects, and higher zeta potential values.

The results of the MTT assay showed that the samples synthesized using both glycine and citric acid did not harm the growth and proliferation of MG-63 cells after 7, 14, and 21 days of incubation. Furthermore, the proliferation of MG-63 cells in the powders synthesized using glycine and doped with 0.1 mole Si^{4+} ions was significantly higher than in the control samples.

Another example is related to the CaPs doped by Sr^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , and Ti^{4+} ions [90]. The data on the crystallinity, specific surface area, and average particle size are presented in Table 10. It can be seen that in all cases, particle size was below 100 nm. Interestingly, low-dose doping (0.1 moles) decreases particle size and significantly enhances the specific surface area, while high doping (0.5 moles) results in the opposite effect.

Table 10. Semi-quantification results on crystallinity, phases, crystallite and particle size (adopted from [90])

Fuel	Amount dopant, mole	Crystallinity %	HA wt. %	β TCP wt. %	Crystallite Size, nm	BET. m^2/g	Particle size, nm
Un-doped	0	59	90	10	60 ± 4	37	68 ± 6
Sr-doped	0.1	59	91	9	60 ± 4	79	39 ± 2
	0.5	53	93	7	51 ± 6	23	69 ± 3
Fe-doped	0.1	60	90	10	50 ± 3	65	24 ± 6
	0.5	55	87	13	41 ± 5	23	60 ± 6
Ti-doped	0.1	58	88	12	47 ± 9	106	29 ± 5
	0.5	41	84	16	38 ± 13	66	74 ± 16

Since nanoparticles with larger surface area, smaller particle size, and higher surface charge should possess better biological performance, the cell viability of samples doped with 0.1 mole of dopants was evaluated using the MTT assay. The results show that the dopants have no noticeable effects on the MG-63 osteosarcoma cell viability, suggesting that doped CaPs are cytocompatible system. In addition, the in vitro cell-based results indicate that CaPs and theranostic ions doped CaPs have a significant impact on the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). The CaPs alone led to the increase of intracellular ROS generation by about 60%. The doped CaPs with Sr^{2+} , Fe^{2+} , and Ti^{4+} ions resulted in an even more significant improvement in intracellular ROS generation (Figure 20).

Figure 20. The reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation results of doped CaPs with 0.1 mol of theranostic ions. The fluorescent microscope images (a) and the results of ROS quantification (b) (adopted from [90]).

Thus, it was demonstrated that CaP-based ceramics can be successfully fabricated directly by the SCS method. Particle size can be varied in the range of 20-80 nm. Synthesized materials showed attractive biomedical properties.

4. Challenges and Tasks

The SCS is a powerful tool for synthesizing materials suitable for biomedical applications. It is an energy-saving approach that allows control of the phase composition and morphology of the synthesized particles. However, significant work should still be accomplished to move this method from the attractive and prospective method to laboratory-scale or industrial technologies.

The SCS is based on the paradigm of self-sustained reactions and has specific relations to conventional approaches mentioned in the introduction. Indeed, all parameters of this method, i.e., temperature, pressure, time, rate of chemical reactions, etc., are strongly correlated. For example, one cannot change process temperature, keeping the characteristic processing time constant. Thus, using a trial and error approach to optimize the process is challenging - too many strongly correlated parameters. The precise control of the structure and, thus, properties of the synthesized materials is possible only based on the fundamental knowledge of the phenomenon.

Combustion synthesis (CS) has over fifty years of history (cf. [91,92]). During this time, a solid theoretical basis has been established, which allows us to predict and explain experimental observations on the synthesis of various materials [93, 94, 64, 95]. Many in-situ and operando diagnostics were developed to investigate the phenomenon of self-sustained reactions [91, 96]. It was proven that while synthesis conditions are unique, i.e., extremely high temperatures and rate of temperature change in the reaction front, during CS, one can use well-acknowledged mechanisms for new phase formation [96]. Unfortunately, analysis of the literature shows that only a few teams in the world are using these priceless accumulations. It is noticeably related to the field of solution combustion synthesis.

Typically, the SCS works involve preparing the reactive solutions with different fuel-to-oxidizer ratios. The solution is subjected to high-temperature treatment by using different heating sources (furnace, hot plate, microwave, etc.). The properties of the product, obtained after initiation of self-sustained reactions (90% of the time in so-called thermal explosion mode), were carefully analyzed. Easy and low-cost, enough to make paper, not enough to make technology.

The thermal explosion or volume combustion synthesis (VCS) mode is less controllable than other CS modes shown in Figure 2. All self-propagating high-temperature synthesis (SHS) modes are much easier to direct and thus optimize. Thus, we recommend using SHS mode for the SCS of the materials.

The temperature of the preheating device does not characterize the temperature of the formation of new phases during SCS. It is typically defined as the temperature of the surrounding atmosphere responsible for the cooling stage after the reaction. The temperature-time history of the SCS process should be monitored by thermocouple or pyrometric measurements (e.g., see Figure 3). The latter is critical to any research that aims to develop reliable technology. The temperature of the furnace, ignition temperature, adiabatic combustion temperature, and maximum combustion temperature are different parameters that influence the mechanism of the reaction and thus define the material's properties. Thus, their values should be calculated and measured in every research work. The adiabatic combustion temperature depends on the equilibrium phase composition of the products, which can be different for the same system but various fuel-to-oxidizer ratios, amount of water, or surrounding atmosphere (see Figure 1). Thus, it is critical to calculating the thermodynamic equilibrium phase composition, followed by an estimation of the adiabatic combustion temperature.

609 In general, the ignition temperature of the reactive systems is not the characteristic
610 value, i.e., it may change with changing the preheating and heat loss conditions [91, 96].
611 However, it was shown that this temperature is often related to the decomposition tem-
612 peratures of the fuel or oxidizer. It is recommended to analyze these values for each sys-
613 tem under study. The latter allows one to control reaction initiation conditions, essential
614 for controlling the structure formation mechanism.

615 It is vital to understand that the combustion mechanism involves gas phase reactions
616 between the gaseous species formed during the decomposition of fuel and oxidizer. The
617 reaction atmosphere may have a reduction or oxidative nature, which influences the com-
618 position of the final product. Controlling the nature of the gaseous combustible atmos-
619 phere is powerful in controlling the product's phase composition. Studying the combus-
620 tion mechanism is an essential task for research in SCS.

621 One advantage of the SCS is the ability to direct fabrication of the materials with
622 desired properties, avoiding long-term post-combustion calcination stages. Optimization
623 of the synthesis conditions allows to accomplish this task essentially for any considered
624 products.

625 The unique conditions of SCS and the ability to form desired organic complexes from
626 the reactive solutions permit the fabrication of the metastable phases [56, 59, 74]. A deeper
627 understanding of the intrinsic reaction mechanism will allow the extension of the list of
628 such unique phases, which are impossible to produce by conventional approaches. In gen-
629 eral, the task of the SCS community is to work on SCS-based approaches to produce not
630 only oxides but also metals, alloys, carbides, nitrides, etc. Some of the successful examples
631 are available in the literature (see review [55]).

632 In conclusion, the SCS is an effective unique route for fabricating various nanoparti-
633 cles suitable for different applications, including the biomedical field. However, to reach
634 the final goal, i.e., to design practical controllable approaches, the researchers should pay
635 more attention to the fundamentals of the phenomena. All diagnostics and approaches
636 are well known. It is vital to use them to develop energy-saving, continuous green tech-
637 nologies.

638
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